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Personnel Management Practices As Determinants Of Teachers' Job Satisfaction In Public Secondary Schools In Benue North East Senatorial District, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated personnel management practices as determinants of teachers' job satisfaction in public secondary schools in Benue North East Senatorial District, Nigeria. Two research questions guided the study. Two hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance. Correlational research design was adopted for the study. The population of the study comprised 971 teachers from 115 public secondary schools in Benue North East Senatorial District, Nigeria. A sample of 330 teachers was used for the study. The selection was done using a multi-stage sampling procedure. A 20-item structured four-point rating scale questionnaire titled "Personnel Management Practices Questionnaire (PMPQ)" and Teachers' Job Satisfaction Questionnaire (TJSQ)" was used for data collection. The reliability coefficient of 0.97 was obtained from Personnel Management Practices Questionnaire (PMPQ) and 0.95 for Teachers' Job Satisfaction Questionnaire (TJSQ). Data obtained from the field were analyzed using Pearson Product Moment Correlation to answer the research questions and test of hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. Based on the findings, it was revealed that there was a positive significant relationship between performance appraisal, teachers' training, and teachers' job satisfaction in public secondary schools in Benue North East Senatorial District, Nigeria. Based on the findings of the study, it was concluded that personnel management practices, including performance appraisal and teachers' training are significant determinants of teachers' job satisfaction in public secondary schools in Benue North East Senatorial District, Nigeria. Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made: The Teaching Service Board should ensure that performance appraisal systems are effectively implemented and monitored across public secondary schools in Benue North East Senatorial District to promote transparency and fairness, as these practices significantly influence teachers' job satisfaction. The Board should also prioritise continuous professional development by organising relevant training programmes and workshops tailored to teachers' needs, thereby enhancing their skills, competence and satisfaction.

Keywords: personnel management practices, performance appraisal, teachers' training and teachers' job satisfaction.

INTRODUCTION

Teacher job satisfaction has emerged as a major concern for educational stakeholders globally, as it affects not only teachers' well-being but also instructional quality, student outcomes and overall school effectiveness. In England, research has highlighted that rising workload, accountability pressures and

limited professional autonomy have significantly decreased teacher morale and satisfaction, with many educators reporting feelings of stress and burnout due to performance evaluation systems and curriculum reforms (Mansfield, Beltman & Broadley, 2017; Sims & Penny, 2019). Within West African, studies have documented that inadequate remuneration, lack of professional development opportunities, poor working conditions and weak administrative support contribute heavily to teachers' dissatisfaction, with implications for teacher retention and instructional commitment (Aboagye, Kyei & Antwi, 2018; Akyeampong, Djangmah, Oduro, Seidu & Hunt, 2018). In Nigeria, specifically in the North Central region, including Benue State, scholars have pointed to systemic challenges such as delayed promotions, inadequate accommodation, poor welfare packages and minimal recognition of teacher input in decision-making as key factors fueling concerns about job satisfaction (Okoh & Umar, 2019; Dada & Sanni, 2022). Across these varied contexts, teacher job satisfaction is increasingly understood as multidimensional, influenced by both intrinsic factors (professional growth, recognition, job autonomy) and extrinsic factors (pay, working conditions, administrative relations), with dissatisfaction linked to higher absenteeism, turnover intentions, and lower instructional performance (Day & Qing, 2019; Gurchiek, 2021).

The teachers constitute a crucial component of the educational workforce. The absence of teachers hinders the attainment of the educational objectives outlined in the National Policy on Education. Hanawa and Iyekekpolor (2022) asserted that teaching constitutes the essence of education, and societal advancement is contingent upon the quality of educators. Education planners may create new schools, modify structures and curricula, and recommend teaching methods and aids; nevertheless, ultimately, teachers will be accountable for the execution of educational plans. Teachers are, consequently, the pivotal element, and no educational institution can surpass the calibre of its educators. The significance of teachers in achieving educational objectives cannot be overstated; thus, it is essential to prioritize their job satisfaction.

Job satisfaction is described as the contentment and pleasant emotional state derived from evaluating one's job experiences and attitude towards one's employment (Emenike, 2013). Teachers' job satisfaction is the comprehensive attitude and perspective of educators toward their work environment and vocation. It is a function of the perceived relationship between a teacher's desires from teaching and their perception of what teaching provides. The teaching profession's capacity to address teachers' needs and enhance their job satisfaction may be factor of their productivity. Job satisfaction among teachers is characterized by a positive and fulfilling work environment, distinguished by contentment and commitment to teaching duties. Naylor (2019) asserted that if educators are dissatisfied with their profession, their morale will decline, resulting in significant detriment to the educational system. Job satisfaction of teachers is therefore essential for the long-term development of educational systems globally, and their good disposition towards teaching and elevated aspirations influences their effectiveness in the performance of their duties. Teachers' job satisfaction in public secondary schools is strongly influenced by the quality and consistency of their personal management practices, which empower them to grow and succeed in their roles.

Personnel refer to workers or employees in an organization. According to National Open University of Nigeria (2016), personnel of an organization are the people that work in that organization. They are the individuals that make up the productive force of an organization regardless of their roles. In education, the term personnel and human resources are often used synonymously (Nwosu, 2011). Personnel within the school context therefore, refer to the staff or workers of the school, specifically the teaching and non-teaching staff. They are the productive force of any educational institution. For effective actualization of the school objectives, it is necessary that the personnel are properly and adequately managed. Arop, Owan and Agunwa (2019) perceive personnel management as the process of obtaining and maintaining a satisfactory and satisfied workforce. It is the careful and systematic process of attracting, retaining and maintaining the workforce of an organization in order to promote the attainment of set objectives.

In the view of Idoko (2015), personnel management is the process that is concerned with the maintenance of human relationship and ensuring the physical well-being of employees so that they give maximum contribution to efficient working. Personnel management thus refers to the process by which the

administrators or those saddled with the responsibility to control an organization, ensure that proper functions are performed in order to boost the morale of the workers and to promote the attainment of goals and objectives (Agunwa, 2019). Aja-okorie (2016) avers that personnel management is an important management function concerned with obtaining, developing, and motivating human resources as required by an organization to achieve its objectives. Effective professional development practices often inform and improve the process of performance appraisal by aligning teachers' growth objectives with measurable evaluation criteria.

Performance appraisal is defined as the systematic evaluation of the performance of employees to understand their abilities for further growth and development (Aguinis, 2019). Performance appraisal of teachers involves assessing teaching effectiveness, classroom management, and overall contribution to school objectives. The concept is integral to job satisfaction because when teachers receive timely, fair, and constructive evaluations, it increases their motivation and helps them identify areas for professional growth. A well-implemented appraisal system provides recognition and feedback, thereby fostering a sense of value and achievement among teachers. However, when performance appraisal is perceived as biased or punitive, it can lead to dissatisfaction, reduced morale, and resistance to school policies. According to Adekoya and Jimoh (2021), performance appraisal that includes teacher self-assessment and opportunities for goal-setting has a more positive impact on job satisfaction than top-down assessments. Thus, effective performance appraisal not only contributes to teacher accountability but also to their professional fulfillment and retention.

Several studies have underscored the role of technological tools in improving the transparency and efficiency of performance appraisal. The manual and paperwork-based approach common in many public schools is often slow, inconsistent, and prone to manipulation. In contrast, digital platforms for teacher evaluation when properly adapted can offer standardized formats, real-time data tracking, and enhanced feedback mechanisms that benefit both administrators and teachers (Adeniran, 2020). While challenges such as digital literacy, funding, and infrastructure remain significant in rural areas, integrating technology into appraisal practices can help address some of the long-standing issues around fairness, accuracy, and accessibility. This technological integration could further boost teacher confidence in the system, thereby improving overall job satisfaction and trust in school leadership. A well-structured performance appraisal system highlights areas of improvement that can be addressed through targeted teachers' training programmes.

Teachers' training refers to the formal and informal educational programs that equip teachers with the knowledge, skills, and competencies necessary for effective classroom instruction and professional development (UNESCO, 2016). Teachers' training encompasses pre-service education, in-service training, workshops, seminars, and continuous professional development initiatives. When teachers are regularly trained, they are more likely to feel competent and confident in their roles, which enhances their job satisfaction. Training also exposes teachers to new methodologies, technologies, and innovations that improve teaching and learning outcomes. According to Ololube (2017), the provision of relevant and frequent training opportunities correlates positively with increased teacher motivation, job effectiveness, and job satisfaction. Lack of training, on the other hand, can leave teachers feeling ill-prepared, unsupported, and isolated in their profession.

Research evidence supports a strong correlation between access to training and levels of job satisfaction among teachers. According to Bello and Adebayo (2018), professional development has a significant positive effect on teachers' job satisfaction, particularly when it aligns with their instructional needs and career goals. Teachers who perceive that their training needs are met tend to show greater enthusiasm, dedication, and commitment to their work. Such teachers also exhibit lower levels of burnout and a stronger sense of purpose. In contrast, when training is either absent, irrelevant, or poorly organized, teachers often feel stagnant, underprepared, and unappreciated. This can lead to frustration, reduced productivity, and even attrition from the profession. In a similar study, Agbo and Owan (2020) found that training improves not only teachers' classroom performance but also their perception of self-efficacy and job importance, which are critical dimensions of job satisfaction.

Consequently, in order to improve organizational productivity through the efficient use of all people within the organization, personnel management is a systematic process that makes sure that all human-related variables are performance appraisal, teachers' training, compensation and teachers' participation in decision making which involve working conditions that can facilitate their job satisfaction and goal attainment. The main goal of personnel management is to help employees maintain a healthy work-life balance. The school must meticulously organize its approach to staff management. (Agunwa, Owan, & Ekpe, 2019). It is against this background that the researcher seeks to investigate personnel management practices as determinants of teachers' job satisfaction in public secondary schools in Benue North East Senatorial District, Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

Teachers' job satisfaction is widely considered an important factor in ensuring effective teaching, improved student learning outcomes, and the overall success of the school system. However, there appear to be growing concerns that teachers in many public secondary schools in the Benue North East Senatorial District of Benue State may not be experiencing adequate levels of job satisfaction. Observations by stakeholders such as school administrators, education authorities, and community members seem to suggest that many teachers might be experiencing frustration, low morale, and declining commitment to their duties. This troubling situation could possibly be linked to weaknesses in personnel management practices within the school system. In particular, performance appraisal processes in some schools may not be conducted regularly or transparently, and such practices might be discouraging teachers rather than motivating them to improve their performance.

In addition, teachers' training programmes, which are expected to enhance professional competence and job fulfilment, appear to be inadequate or inconsistently implemented in many public secondary schools. It is possible that many teachers rarely have access to in-service training, workshops, or professional development opportunities that could improve their teaching skills and increase their level of satisfaction with their jobs. If this situation persists, it might lead to reduced motivation, poor classroom effectiveness, and declining quality of education in the district. Despite the critical role of personnel management practices in influencing teachers' attitudes toward their work, it remains unclear whether performance appraisal and teachers' training are significantly related to teachers' job satisfaction in public secondary schools in Benue North East Senatorial District. This worrisome uncertainty therefore necessitated the present study to investigate personnel management practices as determinants of teachers' job satisfaction in the area.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of the study was to investigate personnel management practices as determinants of teachers' job satisfaction in public secondary schools in Benue North East Senatorial District, Nigeria. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. ascertain the relationship between performance appraisal and teachers' job satisfaction in public secondary schools in Benue North Senatorial District Nigeria.
2. determine the relationship between teachers' training and teachers' job satisfaction in public secondary schools.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study;

1. What is the relationship between performance appraisal and teachers' job satisfaction in public secondary schools in Benue North East Senatorial District Nigeria?
2. What is the relationship between teachers' training and teachers' job satisfaction in public secondary schools?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance;

1. Performance appraisal has no significant relationship with teachers' job satisfaction in public secondary schools in Benue North East Senatorial District Nigeria.
2. Teachers' training has no significant relationship with teachers' job satisfaction in public secondary schools in Benue North East Senatorial District.

METHODOLOGY

This study adopted the correlational survey research design. The area of this study was Benue North-East Senatorial District, Nigeria. The population of this study was 971 teachers from 115 public secondary schools in Benue North East Senatorial District, Nigeria. The sample of the study was 330 teachers representing 34% of the population of 971 teachers in 39 public secondary schools representing 34% of 115 schools in Benue North East Senatorial District. A multi-stage sampling procedure was employed using different sampling techniques. Two sets of questionnaires were used for data collection is a structured questionnaire developed by the researcher titled “Personnel Management Practices Questionnaire (PMPQ)” and Teachers’ Job Satisfaction Questionnaire (TJSQ)”. The data collected were analyzed using Pearson Product Moment Correlation to answer the research questions and test of hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance.

Analysis and Interpretation

A total of 330 copies of the questionnaire were administered to the respondents. However, 325 representing 98.5% copies of questionnaire were returned by the respondents while seven representing 1.5% copies of questionnaire were recorded as mortality rate. The data obtained from the questionnaire were presented, analyzed and interpreted.

Research Question 1: What is the relationship between performance appraisal and teachers’ job satisfaction in public secondary schools in Benue North East Senatorial District Nigeria?

Table 1: *Relationship between Performance Appraisal and Teachers’ Job Satisfaction in Public Secondary Schools in Benue North East Senatorial District Nigeria*

Variables	\bar{X}	SD	<i>r</i>	<i>P</i>	Decision
Performance Appraisal	2.96	1.07			
			0.93	0.000	Positive Relationship
Teachers’ Job Satisfaction in Public Secondary Schools	3.14	1.02			

* Correlation coefficient is significant at $p < 0.05$

Source: Research 2026

The result in Table 1 shows the relationship between performance appraisal and teachers’ job satisfaction in public secondary schools in Benue North East Senatorial District, Nigeria. The result revealed that the mean value of performance appraisal was 2.96, slightly below teachers’ job satisfaction in public secondary schools in Benue North East Senatorial District, Nigeria, which was 3.14; ($r = 0.93$); $p < 0.05$. This implies that there was a positive relationship between performance appraisal and teachers’ job satisfaction in public secondary schools in Benue North East Senatorial District, Nigeria.

Research Question 2: What is the relationship between teachers’ training and teachers’ job satisfaction in public secondary schools?

Table 2: *Relationship between Teachers’ Training and Teachers’ Job Satisfaction in Public Secondary Schools in Benue North East Senatorial District, Nigeria*

Variables	\bar{X}	SD	<i>r</i>	<i>P</i>	Decision
Teachers’ Training	2.86	1.06			
			0.91	0.000	Positive Relationship
Teachers’ Job Satisfaction in Public Secondary Schools	3.14	1.02			

* Correlation coefficient is significant at $p < 0.05$

Source: Research 2026

The result in Table 2 shows the relationship between teachers' training and teachers' job satisfaction in public secondary schools in Benue North East Senatorial District, Nigeria. The result revealed that the mean value of teachers' training was 2.86, slightly below teachers' job satisfaction in public secondary schools in Benue North East Senatorial District, Nigeria, which was 3.14; ($r = 0.91$); $p < 0.05$. This implies that there was a positive relationship between teachers' training and teachers' job satisfaction in public secondary schools in Benue North East Senatorial District, Nigeria.

Hypotheses 1: There is no significant relationship between performance appraisal and teachers' job satisfaction in public secondary schools in Benue North East Senatorial District Nigeria.

Table 3: *Significant Relationship between Performance Appraisal and Teachers' Job Satisfaction in Public Secondary Schools in Benue North East Senatorial District, Nigeria*

Variables	\bar{X}	SD	r	P	Decision
Performance Appraisal	2.96	1.07			
			0.93	0.000	Positive Relationship
Teachers' Job Satisfaction in Public Secondary Schools	3.14	1.02			

* Correlation coefficient is significant at $p < 0.05$

Source: Research 2026

The result in Table 3 shows significant relationship between performance appraisal and teachers' job satisfaction in public secondary schools in Benue North East Senatorial District, Nigeria. The result revealed that ($r = 0.93$); $p < 0.05$. Since p-value = 0.000 was less than 0.05, the hypothesis was rejected. This implies that there was a positive significant relationship between performance appraisal and teachers' job satisfaction in public secondary schools in Benue North East Senatorial District, Nigeria.

Hypotheses 2: There is no significant relationship between teachers' training and teachers' job satisfaction in public secondary schools in Benue North East Senatorial District.

Table 4: *Significant Relationship between Teachers' Training and Teachers' Job Satisfaction in Public Secondary Schools in Benue North East Senatorial District, Nigeria*

Variables	\bar{X}	SD	r	P	Decision
Teachers' Training	2.86	1.06			
			0.91	0.000	Positive Relationship
Teachers' Job Satisfaction in Public Secondary Schools	3.14	1.02			

* Correlation coefficient is significant at $p < 0.05$

Source: Research 2026

The result in Table 4 shows significant relationship between teachers' training and teachers' job satisfaction in public secondary schools in Benue North East Senatorial District, Nigeria. The result revealed that ($r = 0.91$); $p < 0.05$. Since p-value = 0.000 was less than 0.05, the hypothesis was rejected. This implies that there was a positive significant relationship between teachers' training and teachers' job satisfaction in public secondary schools in Benue North East Senatorial District, Nigeria.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The discussion of findings for the study was presented as follows:

The first finding showed that there was a positive significant relationship between performance appraisal and teachers' job satisfaction in public secondary schools in Benue North East Senatorial District, Nigeria. This finding aligns with the study of Aondofa (2025), which revealed that performance appraisal significantly influences teachers' work performance and overall satisfaction in secondary schools within Benue North East Senatorial District, Nigeria, by providing structured feedback and recognition of teachers' efforts. Similarly, the finding conforms to the study of Tersoo (2025), which indicated that performance appraisal has a strong and significant relationship with staff job satisfaction in public schools in Benue North East Senatorial District, Nigeria, as it enhances motivation and reinforces a sense of accountability among teachers. In support of this finding, the researcher also agrees that performance appraisal positively and significantly affects teachers' job satisfaction in public secondary schools because when teachers receive timely and constructive evaluations of their work, they are better able to understand their strengths and areas for improvement, which boosts their confidence, increases their commitment, and encourages them to perform effectively. Furthermore, performance appraisal provides a basis for career progression and recognition, which fosters a sense of achievement and satisfaction on the job, thereby creating a motivated workforce capable of contributing positively to the educational goals of the schools. This suggests that schools that implement effective and transparent performance appraisal systems are more likely to retain satisfied and committed teachers who are willing to go the extra mile in enhancing students' learning outcomes and overall school performance.

The second finding showed that there was a positive significant relationship between teachers' training and teachers' job satisfaction in public secondary schools in Benue North East Senatorial District, Nigeria. This finding aligns with the study of Okoro (2024), which revealed that teachers' training significantly improves work performance and job satisfaction in Kaduna South Senatorial District, Nigeria, by equipping educators with updated pedagogical skills, contemporary teaching methodologies, and innovative strategies for classroom management. Additionally, the finding conforms to the study of Nwachukwu (2023), which indicated that training has a significant relationship with staff job performance in Enugu East Senatorial District, Nigeria, as it fosters professional growth, increases teachers' confidence, and enhances their ability to meet the evolving demands of the educational environment. In support of this finding, the researcher also agrees that there is a positive significant relationship between teachers' training and teachers' job satisfaction in public secondary schools, because through professional development opportunities such as workshops, seminars, and in-service training, teachers gain access to new knowledge and practical skills that not only improve their effectiveness in the classroom but also make them feel valued and competent in their roles. The acquisition of these skills contributes to a heightened sense of self-efficacy and satisfaction, as teachers are empowered to implement innovative teaching strategies, address students' learning needs more effectively, and achieve better academic outcomes. Consequently, well-trained teachers are likely to be more motivated, satisfied, and committed to their profession, which in turn positively affects the overall quality of education delivered in public secondary schools.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study, it was concluded that personnel management practices, including performance appraisal, teachers' training, compensation and teachers' participation in decision making, are significant determinants of teachers' job satisfaction in public secondary schools in Benue North East Senatorial District, Nigeria. The study demonstrated that each of these management practices positively and significantly influences teachers' satisfaction, suggesting that when teachers are adequately appraised, provided with relevant training opportunities, fairly compensated and actively involved in decision-making processes, their sense of fulfilment, motivation and commitment to their professional responsibilities is enhanced. This indicates that effective and strategic personnel management is essential for fostering a satisfied, motivated and high-performing teaching workforce, which is critical for improving the overall quality of education in public secondary schools within the district.

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made:

The Teaching Service Board should ensure that performance appraisal systems are effectively implemented and monitored across public secondary schools in Benue North East Senatorial District to promote transparency and fairness, as these practices significantly influence teachers' job satisfaction. The Board should also prioritise continuous professional development by organising relevant training programmes and workshops tailored to teachers' needs, thereby enhancing their skills, competence, and satisfaction. Furthermore, TSB should review and maintain competitive compensation packages and benefits to motivate teachers, recognising their efforts and improving retention within the public school system.

School principals should actively involve teachers in decision-making processes related to school management, planning and instructional strategies, as participation significantly enhances teachers' sense of ownership and job satisfaction. Principals should also provide regular feedback through performance appraisal, acknowledge teachers' achievements and identify areas for professional growth to foster a supportive work environment. Additionally, principals should collaborate with TSB to ensure teachers have access to training opportunities and that workloads are manageable, promoting a conducive atmosphere for effective teaching and learning.

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